

Magneto-resistance Properties of $\text{BaTi}_{1-x-y}\text{Fe}_x\text{Nb}_y\text{O}_3$ Ceramics

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Abstract:

Magneto-resistance and magnetodielectric permittivity under an applied magnetic field has been investigated to develop a new multifunctional device using multiferroic $\text{Ba}(\text{Ti}_{1-x-y}\text{Fe}_x\text{Nb}_y)\text{O}_3$ (BFNT) material at room temperature. Samples with $x, y = 0, 0.025, 0.05$ and 0.075 were prepared using solid-state reaction method. BFNT has a mixture of tetragonal ($P4mm$) and cubic ($Pm-3m$) phases. The cubic phase fraction is increased with x, y -mole fraction which is revealed from Rietveld refinement.

Magneto-resistance & magnetodielectric studies at different frequencies and P-E, M-H hysteresis loops are also investigated. Large negative magneto-resistance (MR) and magnetodielectric constant (MDC) are observed with the addition of Fe and Nb. Intrinsic and extrinsic contributions play a significant role in the MR and MDC and this has been explained by Maxwell Wagner effect and magnetostriction [1].

Keyword: Ferroelectric properties, magnetic properties, Magnetodielectric and magneto-resistance properties.

Reference

1. Dhiren K. et al J. Appl Phys **114**, 234106 (2013)